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CP violation in heavy-flavour decays

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Abstract

The CKM matrix is the only source of CP violation in the Standard Model. Heavy-flavour decays provide an ideal laboratory to test the CKM mechanism. Some recent highlights in CP violation in heavy-flavour decays from the LHCb and Belle II experiments are presented, including updated measurements of the CKM angles β , γ and ϕ_s , and new results in CP violation in charm decays.

1 Introduction

The fact that charge-parity (CP) symmetry is broken in weak interactions has been known for more than sixty years. The discovery of large CP violation in B^0 decays by BaBar [1] and Belle [2] in 2001 established the CKM mechanism [3, 4] as the leading source of CP violation in the Standard Model (SM). In this theory, quark flavour transitions are fully described by the 3×3 unitary CKM matrix using four parameters, including one irreducible complex phase responsible for CP violation, which are determined from flavour physics data. Study of heavy-flavour decays can access most CKM matrix elements, providing crucial information for precision test of the CKM mechanism. The LHCb and Belle II experiments are playing dominant roles in this field.

The LHCb detector [5] is a forward spectrometer at the Large Hadron Collider, dedicated to the study of b - and c -hadron decays. It has excellent performance in tracking, vertexing and particle identification, and provides an effective b -tagging efficiency of about 5% and a typical time resolution of about 45 fs [6], sufficient for resolving the fast B_s^0 oscillation. LHCb has collected large samples of proton-proton collisions, corresponding to an integrated luminosity of 3 fb^{-1} at a center-of mass energy of 7 and 8 TeV in 2011–2012 (Run 1) and 6 fb^{-1} at 13 TeV in 2015–2018 (Run 2). Based on these data, LHCb has performed extensive studies of beauty and charm decays, and achieved high-precision measurements of CP -violating parameters. This paper summarizes the recent progress using the full LHCb Run 1 and Run 2 data samples.

The Belle II experiment [7] is a super- B factory at SuperKEKB. The Belle II physics program is complementary to that of the LHCb experiment, with unique strengths to study B decays to final states with neutrinos and neutral particles. It provides an effective b -tagging efficiency of about 30% and a typical time resolution of about 1.5 ps for study of B^0 mixing and CP violation. Since the start of operation in 2019, Belle II has collected e^+e^- collision data at the $\Upsilon(4S)$ energy corresponding to an integrated luminosity of more than 360 fb^{-1} . This paper discusses some CP violation measurements based on this initial data sample.

2 Measurement of $\sin 2\beta$

The CKM angle $\beta \equiv \arg(-V_{cd}V_{cb}^*/V_{td}V_{tb}^*)$ is a key parameter to characterize mixing-induced CP asymmetry in B^0 decays, where $V_{qq'}$ represents the relevant CKM matrix element. The time-dependent CP asymmetry in B^0 decays via a $b \rightarrow c\bar{c}s$ transition to a CP eigenstate with eigenvalue η_f follows the relation $A_{CP}(t) \approx \eta_f \sin 2\beta \sin(\Delta m_d t)$, where the approximation assumes no CP violation in the mixing and decay. The effective value of 2β is very sensitive to new physics in B^0 - \bar{B}^0 mixing, making it a flagship measurement for heavy-flavour experiments. Both Belle and BaBar experiments have achieved a precision better than 0.03 combining several $b \rightarrow c\bar{c}s$ decay modes [8, 9]. LHCb measured $\sin 2\beta = 0.760 \pm 0.034$ in $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0$ and $B^0 \rightarrow \psi(2S)K_S^0$ decays using Run 1 data [10], compatible with the world average value $\sin 2\beta = 0.699 \pm 0.017$ [11].

Recently, LHCb updated the $\sin 2\beta$ measurement using the Run 2 data sample. The measured time-dependent CP asymmetry and the fit projection are shown on the left of Figure 1. The direct CP violation parameter, C , is found to be consistent with zero, and mixing-induced CP violation is measured to be $S = \sin 2\beta = 0.717 \pm 0.013(\text{stat}) \pm 0.008(\text{syst})$ [12]. A combination of the LHCb Run 1 and Run 2 results yields $\sin 2\beta = 0.724 \pm 0.014$. With Run 2 data, LHCb overtakes the B factories in the precision of $\sin 2\beta$ measurement (Figure 1 right), and improves the precision of the world average by 35%. The new world average, $\sin 2\beta = 0.708 \pm 0.011$, is consistent with the indirect determinations by the CKMfitter group [13] and UTfit group [14]. LHCb plans to accumulate 300 fb^{-1} of proton-proton collisions after a phase-II upgrade, and improve the precision of $\sin 2\beta$ to 0.003 [15].

Using the $\Upsilon(4S)$ data collected in 2019–2021 and corresponding to 190 fb^{-1} , Belle II has measured the B^0 mass difference $\Delta m_d = 0.516 \pm 0.008(\text{stat}) \pm 0.004(\text{syst}) \text{ ps}^{-1}$ in $B^0 \rightarrow D^{(*)-}\pi^+$ decays [16], and the CP violation parameter $\sin 2\beta = 0.720 \pm 0.062(\text{stat}) \pm 0.016(\text{syst})$ in

Figure 1: Left: asymmetry between B^0 - and \bar{B}^0 -tagged decays as a function of the decay time obtained using LHCb Run 2 data, overlaid with the fit projection; right: comparison of the two-dimensional contours in the C versus S plane from LHCb, BaBar, Belle and Belle II.

the decay $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0$ [17]. Belle II has also reported measurements of effective $\sin 2\beta$ value in penguin-dominated $b \rightarrow s$ transitions, such as $B^0 \rightarrow \phi K_S^0$ [18], $B^0 \rightarrow K_S^0 \pi^0$ [19] and $B^0 \rightarrow K_S^0 K_S^0 K_S^0$ [20]. While being statistically limited, these early measurements demonstrate Belle II's ability to study B^0 mixing and CP violation. It plans to collect 50 ab^{-1} at the $\Upsilon(4S)$ energy, which will enable the key parameter $\sin 2\beta$ to be measured at a precision of 0.005 [7].

3 Measurement of B_s^0 mixing phase ϕ_s

The B_s^0 mixing phase ϕ_s is the counterpart of the B^0 mixing phase 2β . Its value is precisely predicted to be very small in the SM, $\phi_s^{\text{SM}} = -2\beta_s = -0.0368^{+0.0009}_{-0.0006}$ rad [13], where $\beta_s \equiv -\arg(-V_{cb}V_{cs}^*/V_{tb}V_{ts}^*)$, and sensitive to new physics in B_s^0 - \bar{B}_s^0 mixing. The ϕ_s angle can be accessed in time-dependent CP asymmetries in B_s^0 decays to CP eigenstates via $b \rightarrow c\bar{c}s$ transitions. The decay $B_s^0 \rightarrow J/\psi\phi$ is the golden mode to measure ϕ_s . A flavour-tagged time-dependent analysis is required to determine the mixing-induced CP asymmetry $S = \eta_f \sin \phi_s$. In addition, an angular analysis is needed to statistically separate the CP -even and odd components of the $J/\psi\phi$ system. The LHCb, ATLAS and CMS experiments have all measured the ϕ_s parameter and the B_s^0 decay width parameter, $\Delta\Gamma_s$, in $B_s^0 \rightarrow J/\psi\phi$ decays using Run 1 and part of Run 2 data [21–23]. While the ϕ_s values agree well, there is some tension between the three measurements of $\Delta\Gamma_s$. Combining these results with LHCb measurements in other $b \rightarrow c\bar{c}s$ modes leads to the world average $\phi_s = -0.049 \pm 0.019$ rad [11].

Recently, LHCb reported an improved measurement of ϕ_s obtained using the full Run 2 data sample in the decay $B_s^0 \rightarrow J/\psi\phi$ [24]. The left plot in Figure 2 shows the measured time-dependent CP asymmetry. No evidence for CP violation is observed, and the parameters are measured to be $\phi_s = -0.039 \pm 0.022(\text{stat}) \pm 0.006(\text{syst})$ rad and $\Delta\Gamma_s = 0.0845 \pm 0.0044(\text{stat}) \pm 0.0024(\text{syst}) \text{ ps}^{-1}$. A combination with previous independent LHCb measurements in $b \rightarrow c\bar{c}s$ decays yields the LHCb average value, $\phi_s = -0.031 \pm 0.018$ rad. This new result improves the precision of the world average by 15%. As seen in the right plot of Figure 2, the new world average, $\phi_s = -0.039 \pm 0.016$ rad, is dominated by the LHCb measurement and consistent with the indirect determinations [13, 14]. Looking to the future, LHCb aims to achieve a precision of 0.003 rad for ϕ_s after the phase II upgrade using a data sample of 300 fb^{-1} [15].

LHCb has also studied time-dependent CP violation in the penguin-dominated decay $B_s^0 \rightarrow \phi\phi$, which proceeds via a $b \rightarrow s\bar{s}s$ transition and can probe quantum effects of new particles in the loop decay process. Previously, LHCb measured the CP -violating phase, $\phi_s^{s\bar{s}s} = -0.073 \pm 0.115(\text{stat}) \pm 0.027(\text{syst})$ rad [25], using data taken in 2011–2017. A recent update of this analysis using the full Run 1 and Run 2 data samples leads to the improved measurement, $\phi_s^{s\bar{s}s} = -0.074 \pm 0.069$ rad [26]. This is the most precise measurement of mixing-induced CP

Figure 2: Left: asymmetry between B_s^0 - and \bar{B}_s^0 -tagged decays as a function of the decay time obtained using LHCb Run 2 data, overlaid with the fit projection; right: comparison and combination of measurements from different experiments.

asymmetry in any penguin-dominated B decay to date, and agrees with the SM prediction of tiny CP violation [27–29]. The CP -violating parameters are also measured separately for different polarization states of the $\phi\phi$ pair, and no sign of polarization dependence is observed.

4 Measurement of CKM angle γ

The CKM angle $\gamma \equiv \arg(-V_{ud}V_{ub}^*/V_{cd}V_{cb}^*)$ can be measured through interference of $b \rightarrow u$ and $b \rightarrow c$ quark transitions in purely tree-level decays. These measurements are free of new physics effect and provide a SM benchmark, which can be compared to indirect determinations inferred from measurements of other observables sensitive to new physics. Any significant discrepancy will be a clear sign of physics beyond the SM. The golden modes to measure γ are $B \rightarrow Dh$ decays, where h is a charged kaon or pion meson, and D is a superposition of D^0 and \bar{D}^0 mesons, which can be reconstructed in many different modes. Other B decay modes, such as $B \rightarrow D^{*0}h$, are also used to measure γ .

A previous combination of all LHCb measurements sensitive to the angle γ and charm mixing parameters led to the value $\gamma = (65.4^{+3.8}_{-4.2})^\circ$ [30], which dominates the world average of direct measurements, $\gamma = (67 \pm 4)^\circ$ [11]. Since then, some new measurements of γ have emerged. A binned analysis of $B^\pm \rightarrow D[K^\mp\pi^\pm\pi^\pm\pi^\mp]h^\pm$ decays using the full Run 1 and Run 2 data samples and hadronic parameters of D decays from CLEO-c and BESIII [31] has yielded the result $\gamma = (54.8^{+3.8}_{-5.8} +0.6 +6.7)^\circ$ [25], where the first uncertainty is statistical, the second systematic and the third due to the external inputs. This is one of the most precise single measurement to date. A weak constraint on γ is also obtained in $B^\pm \rightarrow D[h^\pm h'^\mp\pi^0]h^\pm$ decays [32]. A new LHCb combination including these two results gives $\gamma = (63.8^{+3.5}_{-3.7})^\circ$ [33], in good agreement with the indirectly determined value $\gamma = (65.7^{+1.3}_{-1.2})^\circ$ [13]. Figure 3 (left) compares the constraints on γ from decays of different B species, showing a tension at 2.2σ level between B^0 and B^+ mesons. Figure 3 (right) shows the continuous improvement of the LHCb γ combination result in the past decade. LHCb aims to improve the γ precision to better than 1° with 50 fb^{-1} from phase-I upgrade and 0.4° with 300 fb^{-1} from phase-II upgrade. To achieve these goals, the hadronic parameters of D decays need be significantly improved, using more quantum-correlated $D\bar{D}$ data from BESIII and the planned Super τ -charm factory [34].

Belle II is starting to contribute to the γ measurement. Through combined analysis of Belle and Belle II data, it has measured $\gamma = (78.4 \pm 11.4 \pm 0.5 \pm 1.0)^\circ$ [35], and obtained CP asymmetries in $B \rightarrow Dh$ decays with $D \rightarrow K_S^0 K^\pm \pi^\mp$ that can be used to constrain γ [36]. Belle II is expected to measure γ with a precision of $1\text{-}2^\circ$ using 50 ab^{-1} of data [7].

Figure 3: Left: the 1–CL value as a function of γ from the combination using inputs from B_s^0 , B^0 and B^+ mesons and all species together; right: evolution of the LHCb γ combination result.

Figure 4: Central values and confidence regions in the $a_{\pi^-\pi^+}^d$ vs $a_{K^-K^+}^d$ plane for the LHCb results obtained with data taken during 2010–2018 and 2010–2012.

5 Measurement of direct CP violation in charm decays

In 2019, LHCb observed significant CP violation in the difference between the time-integrated CP asymmetries in $D^0 \rightarrow K^+K^-$ and $D^0 \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-$ decays, $\Delta A_{CP} = (-15.4 \pm 2.9) \times 10^{-4}$ [37], using the Run 2 data sample. The quantity ΔA_{CP} could receive contributions from the decay amplitudes, the mixing and the interference of decay and mixing, but the exact breakdown is unknown. Recently, LHCb measured the time-integrated CP asymmetry in the decay $D^0 \rightarrow K^+K^-$ using the same data sample [38]. Combining this result with the ΔA_{CP} measurement determines the direct CP asymmetries in the two decay processes. The obtained value for $D^0 \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-$ is $a_d(\pi^+\pi^-) = (23.2 \pm 6.1) \times 10^{-4}$, which is 3.8σ from zero (Figure 4). This is the first evidence for direct CP violation in D^0 decays. LHCb also searched for direct CP violation in the decays $D^0 \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-\pi^0$ [39], $D_{(s)}^+ \rightarrow K^-K^+K^+$ [40] and $D^0 \rightarrow h^+h^-\mu^+\mu^-$ [41], with no evidence found.

6 Summary

Using proton-proton data collected in the first two operation periods, the LHCb experiment has obtained high-precision measurements of CP violation in beauty and charm decays, which all agree with the SM predictions. The Belle II experiment is ramping up and producing interesting results. A deeper investigation of CP violation to fully understand its nature and origin is a long-term effort that requires synergies of LHCb, Belle II and charm experiments as well as theoretical physicists.

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